

Doppler Shift Approximation in Seakeeping Problems: A New Formulation for Ships Advancing at Any Forward Speed

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Abstract. This paper proposes a Doppler shift approximation (DSA) method to simplify the spectrum transformation problem that arises when mapping between the intrinsic and encounter frequency domains in seakeeping computations for ships advancing in a seaway. Generally, the mapping between frequencies can be ambiguous, but this study suggests an analytical, unambiguous, approximate formula for the mapping. The devised DSA formula optimises the mapping of encounter and intrinsic frequencies across all regions of the frequency domains up to a specified frequency upper limit, regardless of ship speed. An assessment is made in simulated sea states for the deviation between the outcomes of the approximate (versus exact) spectral calculations. Additionally, a sensitivity study investigates the influence of the two DSA hyperparameters. Results show that spectral transformations from intrinsic to encounter frequency domains are possible by the DSA formula with acceptable accuracy levels, even when high speeds are considered. This especially has the potential to significantly reduce computational costs and complexities in various response-based sea state estimation techniques on board vessels with non-zero forward speeds.

Key words: *Sea state estimation; Spectral analysis; Vessel response; Inverse Problem; Forward speed*

1. Introduction

For a vessel sailing at a non-zero forward speed, the wave-induced vessel responses oscillate at a frequency ω_e that generally differs from the (intrinsic) wave frequency ω_0 due to the *Doppler shift*. This *encounter frequency* is related to the wave frequency through a simple mathematical formula (given later in Section 2.). Naval architecture textbooks [1, 2, 3] have pointed out the elementary, but rather delicate, issue that arises when dealing with the mapping between the two frequency domains for a vessel advancing in following-to-quartering seas, i.e., with waves encountering the vessel from its aft half-part.

One can visualise the effect of the Doppler shift in wave frequencies in an online animation [4] — a screenshot of which is reproduced in Figure 1. For a user-defined vessel speed and wave encounter angle, the tool illustrates the function $\omega_e = f(\omega_0)$. Considering a given encounter frequency (e.g., $\omega_e = 1$ rad/s in Figure 1), the tool shows a scenario in following seas where the mapping of ω_e into ω_0 results in three different intrinsic frequencies denoted $\omega_{0,1}$, $\omega_{0,2}$, and $\omega_{0,3}$, i.e., three different wave frequencies that will excite the vessel responses at the same excitation frequency ω_e . This means that, in certain wave encounter situations for the speed and encounter angle, inverting the relationship $\omega_e = f(\omega_0)$ will yield not just one but several solutions for ω_0 .

This triple-value feature of the Doppler shift has consequences for several common seakeeping problems involving transformations between the encounter and intrinsic frequency domains. Among others, one important problem is the estimation of the wave-induced response of a vessel in the frequency domain, i.e., in terms of a response spectrum. Standard spectral calculations take advantage of the linear filter theory to estimate the response spectrum by combining a given directional wave spectrum with available Response Amplitude Operators (RAOs) for the ship [2]. This simple approach becomes more complicated when considering an advancing ship, since the response spectrum only has a clear physical meaning in a vessel-fixed reference frame, while the input wave spectrum is often reconstructed from information by weather

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Figure 1: Visualisation of the effect of Doppler shift on wave frequencies [4, 5]. The right-hand side illustrates the mapping between intrinsic wave frequencies (x -axis) and encounter frequencies (y -axis) when waves are observed from a ship with forward speed U at an encounter angle β . The parameters are defined on the left-hand side of the panel.

forecast providers in an Earth-fixed reference frame. A transformation from intrinsic to encounter frequency domains is therefore required in that case, which implies a drastic increase in the complexity of the spectral calculations for following-to-quartering sea conditions. This specific problem is addressed by Nielsen et al. [6, 7, 8], especially providing a pseudo-code to implement the spectral calculations of ship responses affected by the Doppler shift, emphasising here that they employ the *exact* mapping between intrinsic and encounter frequencies.

The Doppler shift becomes particularly tricky to handle in inverse problems related to shipboard sea state estimation. In the ship-as-a-wave-buoy framework developed over the last three decades [9, 10, 11, 12, 13], one would like to estimate the physical characteristics of the local wave system based on measurements of the ship's responses induced in the seaway. For advancing ships, depending on the method, this estimation problem can require the transformation of spectra and/or frequencies from the encounter domain towards the intrinsic domain. In following seas, as mentioned before, there may be (up to) three possible candidates of ω_0 for a single ω_e , which leads to an ill-posed estimation problem. Considering frequency domain methods, prior information typically needs to be injected to overcome the non-uniqueness of the solution in the intrinsic frequency domain, for a (physically) realistic wave spectrum estimate to be obtained. The wave spectrum can be inferred in the intrinsic domain for instance by imposing some condition on the smoothness of the spectral shape as is done in Bayesian modelling algorithms [10], or making use of parametric modelling [11], or following semi-parametric scaling approaches [14] which rely on some prior estimate of sea state parameters like T_z . Additionally, Zago et al. [15] proposed a parametric method to estimate directional wave spectra directly in the encounter frequency domain, based on a parameterisation of encounter wave spectra making use of the Weibull distribution mathematical function. Mounet et al. [16] also estimated the directional wave spectrum in a vessel-fixed reference frame by applying a maximum entropy method in combination with the spectral-residual technique by Brodtkorb et al. [17]. In the last two methods [15, 16], the transformation of the wave spectrum back to the intrinsic frequency domain would be done in a second step, which could make convenient use of the method proposed in the present paper. Finally, time-domain methods, such as those proposed by Takami et al. [12, 18, 19] for real-time on-board applications, could also benefit from a computationally efficient way to transform the frequencies of reconstructed wave profiles between encounter and intrinsic domains. These algorithms involve deeply nested optimisation loops, and incorporating (exact) Doppler shift calculations significantly restricts the range of vessel speeds and relative wave headings for which real-time estimation is feasible.

In contrast to other approaches, which handle the Doppler shift exactly, the frequency transformation problem is simplified here by mathematically proposing a bijective approximation of the function $\omega_e = f(\omega_0)$, thus allowing for a one-to-one mapping between the two frequency domains. This idea was proposed earlier by Mounet et al. [20], and the present paper follows up on the work by upgrading the approximation formula. In its original formulation [20], the *Doppler shift approximation* (DSA) was optimised for selected regions of the intrinsic frequency domain, which resulted in the deviations becoming too large at high speeds in following sea encounters. For this reason, the first version of the DSA was mostly helpful in analysing wave measurements from slow-advancing observation platforms, such as small unmanned surface vehicles or drifting waverider buoys, moving at speeds under, say, 5-7 knots. The main novelty of the present paper lies in establishing a generic formula to approximate the Doppler shift at *any* forward speed.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. After condensing the general theory of wave observations from a vessel-fixed reference (Section 2.), a new DSA formula is derived analytically (Section 3.). The accuracy of spectral calculations by the approximation method and its sensitivity to two hyperparameters are subsequently assessed (Section 4.), considering a numerical example built from time-domain simulations of short-crested wave systems in various encounter situations. Concluding remarks are finally provided (Section 5.).

2. General theory

When sampled over time at a fixed-point location, the sea surface elevation can behave as a stochastic process. The exact shape of the surface cannot be forecast with full certainty [21, 22]. Nonetheless, it is generally assumed that, over a limited-length time window, typically thirty minutes to one hour, and over a restricted spatial domain, the surface waves can be described by a stationary ergodic process, called *sea state*, e.g., Lewis [2]. This assumption – sometimes referred to as the decoupling approach – means that, at a local scale, it is possible to estimate the short-term statistical properties of the wave process from a single recording of the wave elevation at a point location [5].

The linear wave theory assumes that the irregular sea surface elevation ζ about the mean sea level is a random linear superposition of a large number of non-interacting regular wave components, all travelling independently of one another in different directions at different frequencies [1]:

$$\zeta(\mathbf{x}_0, t) = \sum_n a_n \sin(\mathbf{k}_n \mathbf{x}_0^\top - \omega_{0,n}t + \phi_n) \quad (1)$$

where t is the time and $\mathbf{x}_0 = (x_0, y_0)$ are the spatial coordinates in an Earth-fixed reference frame. The wave components are densely distributed in frequency and direction. For the n -th component, a_n is the wave amplitude, $\omega_{0,n}$ the circular frequency, $\mathbf{k}_n = (k_n \cos \mu_n, k_n \sin \mu_n)$ the wavenumber vector, μ_n the direction of travel, and ϕ_n a random phase angle in $[-\pi, \pi)$. The wavenumber and frequency of each component satisfy the linear, deep-water dispersion relation,

$$\omega_{0,n}^2 = gk_n, \quad (2)$$

with g the gravitational acceleration.

Considering that ships are usually advancing at a non-zero forward speed, Equation (1) is updated for the *encountered* wave profiles ζ_e in an inertial reference frame following the vessel's forward motion:

$$\zeta_e(\mathbf{x}_s, t) = \sum_n a_n \sin(\mathbf{k}_n \mathbf{x}_s^\top - \omega_{0,n}t + \phi_n) \quad (3)$$

with $\mathbf{x}_s = \mathbf{x}_0 + Ut(\cos(\chi), \sin(\chi))$. The ship speed U and heading χ are assumed to be constant over time. Equation (3) describes the surface elevation of the undisturbed incident waves that the ship *encounters* along its trajectory.

An equivalent formulation of Equation (3) is obtained by introducing the encounter frequency $\omega_{e,n}$:

$$\zeta_e(\mathbf{x}_0, t) = \sum_n a_n \sin(\mathbf{k}_n \mathbf{x}_0^\top - \omega_{e,n}t + \phi_n), \quad (4a)$$

$$\omega_{e,n} = \omega_{0,n} - \omega_{0,n}^2 \frac{U}{g} \cos(\beta_n), \quad (4b)$$

Figure 2: The Doppler shift of wave frequencies at different values of τ (Equation (5)).

Table 1: Main properties of the (exact) Doppler shift in different wave encounter conditions.

Sea encounter	Angle of encounter β	Doppler param. τ	Function f
Head to bow	$\beta \in (90^\circ - 270^\circ)$	$\tau < 0$	f monotonic
Beam (port or starboard)	$\beta \in \{90^\circ, 270^\circ\}$	$\tau = 0$	f monotonic
Following to quartering	$\beta \in (0^\circ - 90^\circ) \cup (270^\circ - 360^\circ)$	$\tau > 0$	f <u>not</u> monotonic

where the dispersion relation of Equation (2) has been used. Assuming that μ_n is the direction where wave component n is *propagating towards* (oceanographic convention), e.g., relative to the geographical North, then the angle of encounter β_n relative to the ship heading is obtained by $\beta_n = (\chi - \mu_n)$.

Equation (4b) – which is found in many naval architecture textbooks [1, 2, 3] – physically consists of a *Doppler shift* between the (intrinsic) wave frequency $\omega_{0,n}$ and the encounter frequency $\omega_{e,n}$, depending on the ship speed U and the angle of wave encounter β_n . The significance of the Doppler shift effect can be quantified through the quantity $\tau_n = U/g \cos \beta_n$, which is referred to as the *Doppler shift parameter* in this paper. A null value of τ_n means that the Doppler shift has no effect, and the intrinsic and encounter frequencies coincide. On the contrary, a non-zero value of τ_n implies that those two frequencies are different, except at $\omega_{0,n} = \omega_{e,n} = 0$ rad/s, for which the equality of null frequencies always holds.

To simplify the notations, the subscript n is dropped onwards. Moreover, an absolute value is applied to the right-hand side of Equation (4b) to avoid the occurrence of a negative ω_e :

$$\omega_e = f(\omega_0) = |\omega_0 - \omega_0^2 \tau|, \quad (5a)$$

$$\tau = U/g \cos \beta. \quad (5b)$$

Figure 2 illustrates the shape of the curve of $\omega_e = f(\omega_0)$ for different values of τ and Table 1 summarises its main properties. On the one hand, the dark-shaded area in Figure 2 covers the portion of the closed upper half-space (ω_0, ω_e) (with $\omega_0, \omega_e \geq 0$) corresponding to head-to-bow sea scenarios. In that case, ω_e is always greater than ω_0 and there is a one-to-one (invertible) relationship between the one and the other. On the other hand, in the remaining portion of the figure (light-coloured area), corresponding to following-to-quartering sea scenarios, the function f is non-monotonic. Because of the absolute value in Equation (5a), the sign of the slope of the curve $\omega_e = f(\omega_0)$ changes twice in the interval $[0, \infty)$ of ω_0 , and a singularity appears at the point $(\tau^{-1}, 0)$. This is seen in Figure 2, where changes of the slope

sign demarcate three regions of the frequency mapping. The curve is concave in Regions I and II, while Region III features a convex parabolic branch. Therefore, in following-to-quartering sea conditions, a given encounter frequency ω_e can be associated with up to three corresponding (intrinsic) wave frequencies ω_0 . Onwards, this complication will be referred to as the *triple-value problem*; namely, if a wave observation is made in the vessel-fixed reference frame *only*, it is then impossible to exactly trace back the individual contributions of the three incident wave trains that took part in the measured amplitude of a given encountered wave component. The problem is described in detail by Nielsen [14]. It is interesting to note that a triple ω_0 -value arises exclusively for encountered wave components oscillating at a frequency $\omega_e \leq (4\tau)^{-1}$ for $\tau > 0$. On the opposite, for $\omega_e > (4\tau)^{-1}$, $\tau > 0$, the curve of $\omega_e = f(\omega_0)$ is monotonic and a one-to-one relationship can be established between ω_0 and ω_e .

3. Methods

3.1. Formulation of the DSA

In this derivation, all frequency quantities are normalised by a given cut-off frequency $\omega_m > 0$, to be specified:

$$\Omega_0 \equiv \omega_0/\omega_m, \quad (6a)$$

$$\Omega_e \equiv \omega_e/\omega_m, \quad (6b)$$

$$\nu \equiv \tau\omega_m. \quad (6c)$$

The (exact) Doppler shift of Equation (5a) can be rewritten in a normalised form:

$$\Omega_e = h(\Omega_0|\nu) = |\Omega_0 - \nu \Omega_0^2|. \quad (7)$$

The following polynomial P is proposed as an approximation of Equation (7), which will be called *Doppler shift approximation* (abbreviated as DSA) onwards:

$$\Omega_{e,P} = P(\Omega_0|\nu) = (1 - \rho_P) \Omega_0 - \nu_P \Omega_0^2, \quad (8)$$

where (ρ_P, ν_P) are polynomial coefficients to be determined as functions of the nondimensional Doppler shift parameter ν . The polynomial P is a second-order polynomial satisfying the condition $P(0) = 0$, which is required for energy conservation of the low-frequency wave components ($\Omega_0, \Omega_e \sim 0$). As a passing remark, the DSA formula of Equation (8) does *not* involve an absolute value, unlike the exact Doppler shift of Equation (7).

The value of the coefficients that minimises the discrepancies between $\Omega_{e,P}$ and Ω_e is sought after. An essential property of polynomial P is that it must be a strictly increasing function of Ω_0 in the open interval $(0, 1)$ to ensure a one-to-one relationship between Ω_0 and Ω_e . This facilitates the definition of an optimisation problem with the following cost function J to be minimised:

$$J(\rho_P, \nu_P|\nu) = \int_0^1 [h(\Omega_0|\nu) - P(\Omega_0|\nu)]^2 d\Omega_0, \quad (9a)$$

$$\text{s.t., } \forall \Omega_0 \in (0, 1), \forall \nu, P'(\Omega_0|\nu) > 0, \quad (9b)$$

where P' is the first derivative of the polynomial P .

It is important to note that the integral in Equation (9a) applies over the range $[0, 1]$ of Ω_0 . Referring to the definition of Ω_0 in Equation (6a), it appears clearly that the chosen ω_m acts as a cut-off frequency in the optimisation.

Since the cost function has a differentiable closed-form expression (not shown here), it is possible to solve the optimisation problem analytically by posing that the gradient ∇J must be zero at the extremum of J . After some derivations, the following solutions are found, also satisfying both conditions of Equation (9b):

$$\rho_P(\nu) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } \nu \leq \nu_{12}, \\ A_1(\nu) & \text{for } \nu_{12} < \nu < \nu_{23}, \\ 1 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Figure 3: The coefficients of the DSA as a function of the nondimensional variable ν . Here, the threshold value ν_{23} is set to $(1 + \sqrt{2})/2$.

and

$$\nu_P(\nu) = \begin{cases} \nu & \text{for } \nu \leq \nu_{12}, \\ 1/2 - A_1(\nu)/2 & \text{for } \nu_{12} < \nu < \nu_{23}, \\ A_2(\nu) & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

with:

$$A_1(\nu) = \frac{1}{8} \left[3\nu(-4\kappa^5 + 10\kappa^4 - 3) + 15\kappa^4 - 40\kappa^3 + \frac{41}{2} \right], \quad (12a)$$

$$A_2(\nu) = \nu(2\kappa^5 - 1) - \frac{5}{2}\kappa^4 + \frac{5}{4}, \quad (12b)$$

where $\kappa = \min(\nu^{-1}, 1)$.

The coefficients (ρ_P, ν_P) are piecewise functions of the nondimensional Doppler shift parameter ν , like illustrated in Figure 3. They enable the DSA to have the following properties:

1. The DSA is exact ($\Omega_{e,P} = \Omega_e$) when $\nu \leq \nu_{12}$. This is only possible in either head-to-beam sea conditions ($\nu \leq 0$) or when solely Region I contributes to the (exact) Doppler shift over the integration range of the cost function in Equation (9a). The latter condition requires ν_{12} to be aligned with the first change of slope in Figure 2, that is $\nu_{12} = 1/2$.
2. In the interval $\nu \in (\nu_{12}, \nu_{23})$, the DSA is a concave function of Ω_0 , due to a negative leading coefficient of the polynomial P (i.e., $\nu_P > 0$). The concavity of the approximation function matches well with that of the exact Doppler shift mapping in Regions I and II, which are preponderant in this interval of ν values.
3. When $\nu \geq \nu_{23}$, the DSA becomes a convex function of Ω_0 , since $\nu_P < 0$. The convexity choice comes from the convex shape of the (exact) Doppler shift mapping in Region III, which becomes increasingly important when ν becomes larger above the threshold value ν_{23} . There is no strict mathematical requirement on ν_{23} , although it should be noted that only $\nu_{23} \geq 1$ makes physical sense, considering that Region III is completely absent from the Doppler shift mapping for $\Omega_0 \in [0, 1]$ at values of ν lower than 1. All figures in the present section use a threshold value of $\nu_{23} = (1 + \sqrt{2})/2$, which, as was seen in Figure 2, is chosen so that, when $\nu = \nu_{23}$, then the portion of Region III not affected by the triple-value problem starts becoming visible in the range $\Omega_0 \in [0, 1]$.

Figure 4: Exact Doppler shift and the proposed DSA for various values of the nondimensional Doppler shift parameter ν . Here, the threshold value ν_{23} is set to $(1 + \sqrt{2})/2$.

4. When $\Omega_{e,P}$ intersects with the exact Ω_e in Region III, for $\nu > \nu_{23}$, one can then use the exact Ω_e in place of the approximate $\Omega_{e,P}$ since the triple-value problem is no longer an issue past this point. The intersection point is found at $\Omega_0 = (\nu_P + \nu)^{-1}$, equivalently at $\Omega_e = -\nu_P (\nu_P + \nu)^{-2}$.

The properties listed above are confirmed in Figure 4, which plots the DSA mapping compared to the exact one for various values of ν , covering wave encounter scenarios from head seas ($\nu < 0$) to following seas ($\nu > 0$). To give an idea of the orders of magnitude, a value of $\nu = 3$ is reached for $\omega_m = 2$ rad/s when a ship sails in following seas with a forward speed of $U \approx 29$ knots. Additionally, in the 3-D surface plots of Figure 5, the relationship between the wave frequencies and the encounter frequencies at varying ν values is illustrated for the exact (left panel) and approximate (right panel) Doppler shifts. The one-to-one relationship – facilitated by the transitions between different polynomial shapes, depending on ν – is visible in the approximate Doppler mapping.

Considering the proposed DSA in Equation (8), the relationship can be inverted to find an expression of $\Omega_{0,P}$ (note the P -index denoting the approximation) for a given Ω_e :

$$\Omega_{0,P} = \left| \frac{1}{2\nu_P} \left[(1 - \rho_P) - \sqrt{(1 - \rho_P)^2 - 4\nu_P \Omega_e} \right] \right| \quad \text{for } \Omega_e \leq -\nu_P (\nu_P + \nu)^{-2}. \quad (13)$$

The absolute value is needed to ensure that $\Omega_{0,P}$ remains always positive.

3.2. Error in encounter frequencies computed by the DSA

The present formulation of the DSA is optimal in the sense that it minimises the integrated squared error in encounter frequencies, as was expressed in the cost function of Equation (9a). Because the cost function averages the DSA errors over the range $[0, 1]$ of Ω_0 , it remains crucial to assess, individually for each Ω_0 , the magnitude and sign of the error of the corresponding $\Omega_{e,P}$, which also depends on ν . The result is shown in Figure 6 as a colourmap showing the error levels of $\Omega_{e,P}$ with respect to the exact Ω_e . Blue (respectively, red) colours indicate a negative (positive) bias. The three regions of the exact Doppler

Figure 5: Surface plot of the exact (*left panel*) and approximate (*right*) Doppler shift mappings between Ω_0 and Ω_e over a range of ν values.

shift mapping identified earlier in Figure 2 are delimited by the solid black lines. It is observed that the approximation in Region I generally features a (mild) negative bias, which fades away when ν approaches the threshold ν_{12} , below which the approximation becomes exact, as already pointed out. Region III has a positive bias which attenuates when Ω_0 gets closer to the threshold $(\nu_P + \nu)^{-1}$, above which the error is null because the exact encounter frequency Ω_e is then used. In Region II, the error is negative for $\Omega_0 < \rho_P (\nu - \nu_P)^{-1}$, positive otherwise.

The error discontinuity at $\nu = \nu_{23}$ is due to the “switch” between the concave and convex forms of the DSA, operated by the polynomial coefficients (ρ_P, ν_P) in Equations (10) and (11).

4. Numerical example

4.1. Simulated scenarios

The DSA is now applied in a case study to illustrate its accuracy in realistic sea conditions. Eight scenarios of wave encounters in short-crested seas are simulated in the time domain for two different forward speeds ($U = 12$ and 24 knots) and four different prevailing wave headings ($\beta_p = 0^\circ, 60^\circ, 120^\circ,$ and 180°) relative to the direction of forward motion. The simulated sea state corresponds to a generalised JONSWAP spectrum [23] with significant wave height $H_s = 3$ m, peak period $T_p = 8$ s, and peak enhancement factor $\gamma = 1.4$. Directional wave spreading in short-crested seas is modelled by a cosine- $2s$ function with a spreading parameter $s = 8$. The generating (point and directional) wave spectrum is shown in Figure 7 as a function of the intrinsic wave frequency $f_0 = \omega_0/(2\pi)$ and the relative wave heading β . In Figure 7a, the exact mapping between f_0 and f_e at the speed $U = 24$ knots and for the four considered prevailing headings β_p is superimposed on the point wave spectrum plot using a secondary y -axis.

The outcome of the time-domain simulations for each encounter scenario is a set of 30 non-repeating realisations of encountered wave profiles of 2 hours duration each sampled at 2 Hz. Following a numerical setup implementing Equation (4a), each time series is generated with a different random seed; additional details on the numerical setup for the simulations are given in Refs. [7, 8]. It is emphasised that the time-domain simulations are performed using the exact Doppler shift of Equation (4b) for $\omega_{e,n}$. The encountered wave profiles correspond to the surface elevation measured over time by an ideal wave probe advancing at a constant forward speed U . One can compute a fast Fourier transform (FFT) of those time records to obtain a theoretical estimate of the wave spectrum in the encounter frequency domain. Here, the spectrum of the individual realisations is computed via the Welch method [24], applying a Parzen window on subsegments of length $2^{10} = 1024$ discretised samples with a 50% overlap between segments. Subsequently, averaging

Figure 6: Contour map of the DSA error in $\Omega_{e,P}$ with respect to the exact Doppler shift. Here, the threshold value ν_{23} is set to $(1 + \sqrt{2})/2$.

(a) Point wave spectrum and frequency mapping.

(b) Directional wave spectrum.

Figure 7: Generating wave spectrum for simulating the sea state in the numerical example. The frequency mapping (*left panel*) is shown for a speed $U = 24$ knots. The directional wave spectrum (*right panel*) uses the nautical convention, i.e., with the directions indicating where the wave energy comes from, here showing a prevailing relative wave heading of $\beta_p = 180^\circ$ (head seas).

Figure 8: Directional wave spectra transformed to the encounter frequency domain by the DSA in eight wave encounter scenarios. In this case, the cut-off frequency was set to $f_m = \omega_m / (2\pi) = 0.19$ Hz and the threshold ν_{23} to 1.1. The vertical scaling encoded in the contour colours is preserved between the different panels. The nautical convention is used for wave directions; cf. caption of Figure 7.

the computed spectra over the 30 realisations yields a highly accurate estimate of the encounter-domain wave spectrum. The total of $30 \times 2 = 60$ hours of simulated surface elevation data, generated under identical sea state conditions, provides a sufficiently large sample to estimate the point spectrum with high statistical confidence. Therefore, for the simulated scenarios considered, the ensemble-averaged spectrum can be regarded as a reliable ground truth reference.

4.2. DSA results and discussions

In this numerical example, the proposed DSA is used to transform the directional wave spectrum of Figure 7 from the intrinsic frequency domain towards the encounter frequency domain. The technical details of this spectral transformation are omitted for the sake of conciseness. It suffices to say that the calculations implement the DSA formula of Equation (8) and account for energy conservation in the directional wave spectra $E_0(\omega_0, \beta)$ and $E_e(\omega_e, \beta)$ when transforming between the intrinsic and encounter frequency domains, respectively:

$$E_e(\omega_e, \beta) = \left\langle E(\omega_0, \beta) \frac{d\omega_0}{d\omega_e} \right\rangle_{\omega_e} \quad (14)$$

where the angle brackets $\langle \cdot \rangle_{\omega_e}$ indicate that the calculations are performed for a given encounter frequency ω_e – and, implicitly – for a given forward speed U .

The directional spectra obtained in the encounter frequency domain through the DSA transformation are shown in Figure 8. The effect of the Doppler shift on the wave spectra is notable in all eight encounter scenarios with important distortions along the frequency axes, i.e., in the radial direction. In compliance with the theory, the spectrum is shrunk towards lower frequencies for the following-to-quartering wave components, while it is stretched towards higher frequencies for the head-to-bow wave components.

The accuracy of the DSA results is now compared to that of the exact spectral transformation method proposed by Nielsen et al. [6, 7, 8], which employs the exact Doppler shift of Equations (5a) and (5b). The reader is referred to the cited works for details on the numerical procedure on how to exactly transform spectra from intrinsic to encounter frequency domains. It is simply reminded here that this transformation does not hold any ambiguity, regardless of the wave encounter scenarios. The inverse transformation from

Table 2: Normalised errors ϵ_S of the computed encounter-domain spectra in Figure 9 by the DSA and the exact Doppler shift, respectively, with reference to the ground-true spectra.

Speed U	Method	Angle β_p			
		0°	60°	120°	180°
12 knots	DSA	0.564	0.330	0.166	0.175
	Exact	0.357	0.225	0.165	0.175
24 knots	DSA	0.723	0.418	0.199	0.214
	Exact	0.193	0.247	0.191	0.214

encounter to intrinsic frequency domains, however, does not have a unique solution because of the triple-value problem in following-to-quartering sea conditions. This explains why the accuracy of the DSA can only be compared to that of the exact spectral calculation method by assessing the wave spectra transformed to the encounter frequency domain; in theory, the inverse spectral transformation cannot be exact.

While the exact Doppler shift transform is theoretically accurate, its numerical implementation is subject to discretisation and interpolation errors. As demonstrated in the numerical studies by Nielsen et al. [7, 8], achieving a near-perfect match between the transformed and original spectra requires very fine resolution in both frequency and direction. In practical applications, such high resolution is often computationally prohibitive, and the use of coarser grids introduces numerical artefacts that can distort the spectral shape. Consequently, the ensemble-averaged spectrum—derived from high-fidelity time-domain simulations—is used as a reference, making it a more robust and stable benchmark for evaluating the performance of the DSA under realistic computational constraints.

Figure 9 represents several point wave spectra. The blue curve is the encounter-domain spectrum resulting from the exact spectral transformation [6, 7, 8] of the JONSWAP spectrum via the exact Doppler shift. Conversely, the purple line results from using the DSA in the spectral transformation; the point spectra have been obtained by integrating the directional spectra of Figure 8 over all directions β (0-360 degrees). The grey curves represent the 30 wave spectra computed through individual FFTs of the 30 realisations of encountered wave profiles. The bold black curve is an ensemble mean of these 30 spectra and, as mentioned earlier, is considered the ground-true spectrum. The input JONSWAP wave spectrum is also plotted as a thin black line for information purposes only.

The normalised error ϵ_S of the encounter-domain spectrum E_e obtained through spectral transformations is computed with reference to the ground-true spectrum $E_{e,\text{true}}$ as follows:

$$\epsilon_S = \sqrt{\frac{\int_0^\infty |E_{e,P}(\omega_e) - E_{e,\text{true}}(\omega_e)| d\omega_e}{\int_0^\infty E_{e,\text{true}}(\omega_e) d\omega_e}}. \quad (15)$$

The error ϵ_S of the spectra in Figure 9 has been computed for both transformations (DSA and exact) and the values are reported in Table 2.

Overall, it can be said that the spectrum by the exact spectral calculation is in nearly perfect agreement¹ with the ground-true spectrum, which is consistent with the theory. There is also a nearly perfect match between the DSA results and the ground true spectrum in the four encounter scenarios dominated by head-to-bow sea wave components (i.e., $\beta_p = 120^\circ$ and 180°), while discrepancies appear mostly at low frequencies $f_e \lesssim 0.07$ Hz in the other four scenarios dominated by following-to-quartering sea wave components.

It should be noted that an unavoidable limitation of the encounter domain spectra obtained through the DSA is that the power spectral density (PSD) always drops to zero in the vicinity of $\omega_e \rightarrow 0$. This is not necessarily the case for the ground true spectra, as can be seen for instance in the two scenarios $\beta_p = 0^\circ$ and 60° at a speed $U = 24$ knots, where the spectral density reaches a non-zero value at $\omega_e \rightarrow 0$; the spectral transformation using the exact Doppler shift does not suffer from this limitation. The DSA error at low frequencies comes from the fact that the (approximate) encounter frequencies are consistently

¹Discrepancies between results of the exact spectral calculation and the ground truth are entirely due to numerical errors arising from an insufficient resolution in frequency and direction; more information is given in Nielsen et al. [7, 8]. In Figure 9, the spacings $\Delta f_0 = \Delta f_e = 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ Hz and $\Delta\beta = 0.1^\circ$ were used.

Figure 9: Comparison of the transformed (point) wave spectra in eight wave encounter scenarios. In this case, the cut-off frequency was set to $f_m = \omega_m / (2\pi) = 0.19$ Hz and the threshold ν_{23} to 1.1. Note that the scale of the y -axis varies between panels.

(a) Influence of f_m for a fixed $\nu_{23} = 1.1$.

(b) Influence of ν_{23} for a fixed $f_m = 0.19$ Hz.

Figure 10: Sensitivity of the error ϵ_S of the approximate encounter spectrum to the cut-off frequency $f_m = \omega_m/(2\pi)$ and the threshold ν_{23} in the eight considered encounter scenarios (U, β_p) . The corresponding wave spectrum in the intrinsic frequency domain is the JONSWAP spectrum of Figure 7.

overestimated in the vicinity of the junction between Regions II and III of the Doppler shift mapping, where the corresponding (exact) encounter frequencies are near zero. The colourmap of the $\Omega_{e,P}$ -error in Figure 6 showed this positive bias. As could also be seen in Figure 7a, the scenario $(U, \beta_p) = (24 \text{ knots}, 0^\circ)$ of Figure 9 is a particularly difficult case, because the peak frequency $f_p = 1/T_p = 0.125$ Hz then falls in this “blind spot” of the DSA, with $(2\pi \cdot \tau)^{-1} \approx 0.130$ Hz which is very close to f_p .

4.3. Sensitivity study of ω_m and ν_{23}

The respective influences of the cut-off frequency ω_m and the threshold ν_{23} on the normalised error ϵ_S of the encounter spectra obtained through the DSA are investigated in the eight considered encounter scenarios. The results are shown in Figure 10.

Looking first at the right-hand side panel, it can be said that the influence of ν_{23} on the error is marginal, with little variation over the considered range (from 1.00 to 1.32). On the contrary, the left-hand side panel shows a significant influence of $f_m = \omega_m/(2\pi)$ on the errors, especially in following to stern-quartering wave encounter scenarios. For the considered sea state with peak frequency $f_p = 0.125$ Hz represented by the black dotted line, it seems that $f_m \approx 0.19$ Hz would be the optimal value to use to reach the lowest (or nearly lowest) error in all considered encounter scenarios. This corresponds to a ratio of roughly 1.5 between f_m and f_p . For this value of f_m , the spectral peak is located in the (Ω_0, ν) -plane very close to the dashed line shown in Figure 6, which locates occurrences of zero $\Omega_{e,P}$ -error in the DSA following the relation $\Omega_0 = \rho_P (\nu - \nu_P)^{-1}$. This fact points towards the supposition that it might generally be advantageous to select the value of f_m (equivalently, ω_m) such that the peak frequency f_p of the wave spectrum falls within an area of the (Ω_0, ν) -plane having low or null $\Omega_{e,P}$ -error. However, further investigations of the accuracy of DSA-derived spectra in various sea states will need to be made to assess whether this suggested hyperparameter selection rule is generally recommendable, realising that other spectral parameters – such as the peak enhancement factor γ – may also play a determining role in the optimal value of f_m .

5. Conclusions

This study presented a novel Doppler shift approximation (DSA) method for seakeeping computations of ships advancing at any forward speed. The proposed DSA formula offers a one-to-one mapping between encounter and intrinsic wave frequencies, providing an unambiguous and analytical solution that simplifies the spectrum transformation problem. The method’s accuracy was assessed through simulated sea states,

demonstrating acceptable levels of deviation between approximate and exact spectral transformations. The sensitivity study further highlighted the influence of one of the two hyperparameters ω_m on the accuracy of spectral calculations, showing the need for future works to find selection rules for optimal performance.

The findings indicate that the DSA method could significantly reduce computational costs and complexities in response-based sea state estimation techniques, considering measurements on board vessels advancing at speeds (even) above 10 knots. Moreover, this advancement has the potential to enhance on-board expert systems or embedded applications, where computational resources are limited and real-time responsiveness is essential, making the execution cost for exact Doppler calculations prohibitive. The DSA enables rapid frequency transformations, allowing for phase-resolved estimations even under challenging conditions, such as following seas or high-speed transits. Future research should focus on further theoretical studies to validate the applicability of the DSA in various sea states and wave encounter situations. In particular, evaluating the performance of the DSA in the reverse transformation – from encounter frequency (ω_e) back to intrinsic frequency (ω_0) – is a compelling direction for further investigation.

Overall, the DSA method represents a promising step towards more efficient and tractable computations to solve various seakeeping problems, contributing to the advancement of naval architecture and marine engineering.

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